

INNOVATION HUB

INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. They initiate highly relevant research and innovation projects.

Industrial Symbiosis

Target groups: all sectors

Services offered by the NEFI Innovation Hubs

- NEFI Technology Talks:
A range of networking and information events
- Support throughout the entire innovation process: From project idea, application submission, to impact assessment
- Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure
- Effective dissemination and exploitation of solutions and results

Industrial symbiosis promotes cooperation between businesses to enhance efficiency and sustainability and is a key tool for industrial transformation. The use of waste heat improves energy efficiency and CO₂ balance, fostering a circular economy focused on maximising resource utilisation.

KEY FOCUS AREAS

Inter-company use of waste heat or integration into district heating networks

Establishment of energy communities for energy exchange between neighbouring businesses

Creation of networks and partnerships for optimal material cycles and resource efficiency

New business models for shared infrastructure and joint use of resources

CONTACT DETAILS

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HUB CO-LEADS

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